

Reducing inter-subject variability and improving accuracy with standardised Universal Pulses

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Synopsis

Parallel transmission allows flip angle homogenization at ultra-high field. The pulse design process can be made transparent to the user with calibration-free universal pulses (UP) that are designed over a database of field maps. Here a new method is proposed where UPs are designed over a standardized database, i.e. normalized to a reference. During a scan, these standardized UPs (SUPs) are adjusted to the subject through a fast calibration that relies on a linear transformation of the actual B1+ map to the database reference. Adjusted SUPs improve excitation performance and reduce intersubject variability compared to UPs.

Introduction

In parallel transmission (pTX), pulses can either be designed on-the-fly using subject-specific ΔB_0 and B1+ brain field maps, or offline with universal pulses (UP)¹, designed over a database consisting in a set of ΔB_0 and B1+ brain field maps, called pulse design database. UPs allows one to exploit pTX with no scan time overhead (for calibrations), but with a small performance (excitation accuracy) penalty. In this study, a hybrid method is introduced to improve UP performance through a fast subject-specific calibration. In this approach, the B1+ maps of the pulse design database are normalized to a reference B1+ map. The resulting normalized database provides, virtually, a decreased intersubject variability in B1+². So-called standardized UP (SUP) are then designed over the normalized database by strictly following the offline UP design approach. A final adjustment step which will be detailed in the Methods Section is taking place during the MRI session, and consists in optimizing the respective amplitude and phase of the SUP RF waveform using subject-specific B1+ data acquired with a rapid (<10s) scan³⁻⁵. The proposed method allows improving the accuracy of the excitation profiles as demonstrated here with GRAPE pulses⁶ designed for MPRAGE and MP2RAGE sequences. A comparison of T1 maps returned by the adjusted SUP MP2RAGE sequence to the ones returned with the standard CP mode with B1+ correction is also provided⁷, showing one potential application of SUPs .

Theory

Let us consider a pulse design database of ΔB_0 and B1+ maps acquired with N_c transmit coils over N_s subjects:

$$\Delta B_{0,S:1}, B_{+1,S:1}, \dots, \Delta B_{0,S:N_s}, B_{+1,S:N_s}.$$

This pulse design database can be normalized to design a standardized universal pulse (SUP). The first step is to define a reference control field vector $B_{1,Ref}^+$, taken here as the average B1+ over the database, i.e. for every voxel r :

$$B_{1,\text{Ref}}^+(\mathbf{r}) = N_s^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} B_{1,S,i}^+(\mathbf{r}).$$

The second step is to compute, for every subject i of the database, a position-independent $N_c \times N_c$ calibration matrix L_i as the least-squares solution to the problem:

$$\min_{L \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times N_c}} \sum_r \|B_{1,S,i}^+(\mathbf{r}) - LB_{1,\text{Ref}}^+(\mathbf{r})\|_2^2,$$

The standardized transmit field of this subject is then defined in each voxel \mathbf{r} as:

$$\tilde{B}_{1,S,i}^+(\mathbf{r}) = L_i^{-1} B_{1,S,i}^+(\mathbf{r}),$$

whereas the ΔB_0 map is left unchanged. This operation is repeated for every subject of the database.

A SUP (k-space trajectory $k_{\text{SUP}}(t)$, RF waveform $u_{\text{SUP}}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^9$) is then designed on the standardized database using the usual UP design metric (minimisation of the average FA-normalized RMSE). For every new subject i , a calibration matrix L_i is determined as:

$$L_i = \min_L \sum_r \|B_{1,S,i}^+(\mathbf{r}) - LB_{1,\text{Ref}}^+(\mathbf{r})\|_2^2, \text{ subject to: } \forall t, |L^{-1}u_{\text{SUP}}(t)| < V_{\text{max}}$$

where V_{max} is the hardware limit for the RF voltage. The SUP is then adjusted to this subject with the inverse of the calibration matrix:

$$u_{\text{adjSUP}}(t) = L^{-1}u_{\text{SUP}}(t),$$

and (unchanged k-space trajectory):

$$k_{\text{adjSUP}}(t) = k_{\text{SUP}}(t).$$

Since the least squares problem for computing L is overdetermined ($N_c \times N_c$ complex numbers to fit), the calibration matrix can be estimated from a quantitative B_1^+ mapping protocol offering only a partial coverage (e.g. 3 slices) of the entire volume of interest.

Methods

Simulations. A pulse design database with 20 subjects was standardized using the processing steps described above. Nonselective GRAPE UP and SUP were designed offline on this database for the MPRAGE and MP2RAGE sequences (8° excitation and 180° inversion pulses). Excitation performance in terms of fidelity to the target FA of the UP and the adjusted SUP were compared using a test database with 15 subjects.

In vivo application. One volunteer was scanned on a Magnetom 7T scanner equipped with the Nova 8Tx-32Rx head coil. Scans included i) a fast B_1^+ map acquired with a 3-slice turbo-FLASH sequence (5mm resolution, $TA=10s$) ii) two MPRAGE scans using UPs and adjusted SUPs, respectively (TR/TI/TE 2600/1100/2.9ms, resolution 0.8mm, GRAPPA 2, TA 6:51min), and iii) two MP2RAGE scans (adiabatic inversion) using the 8° adjusted SUP and the 8° hard pulse (CP-mode) with TR/TI1/TI2/TE 5000/800/2700/2.84ms, resolution 0.8mm, GRAPPA 3, TA 9:38min. T1 maps were extracted from the MP2RAGE data without and with B_1^+ correction⁷.

Results

Flip angle simulations show more homogeneous and accurate with adjusted SUP as compared to UP. This is shown in Figure 1 for the subject scanned in this study (NRMSE of 7.5% and 9.5% respectively for the 8° adjSUP and UP) and on a control database (see Figure 2). A comparison of the MPRAGE images obtained with UP and adjSUP is shown in Figure 3. In Figure 4, the T1

map computed from the adjSUP-MP2RAGE scan *without* B1+ correction is found to be similar to the one computed from the CP-MP2RAGE scan *with* B1+ correction.

Discussion and conclusion

Adjusted standardized UP allows improving excitation accuracy (reduced FA-NRMSE) thanks to a fast calibration (~10s) scan compared to calibration-less UPs. Additional optimization of the fast 3-slice B1+ mapping protocol would allow decreasing further the calibration time. This technique can be used to perform robust quantitative T1 mapping at 7T without B1+ correction. RF pulse design tailored to the subject can remain bypassed for a whole exam. Scans at higher fields, where B1+ variability is expected to increase, should benefit even more from this method. Future works include extended in vivo validation.

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Figures

Figure 1: Pulse design methodology in the volunteer for the MPRAGE excitation 8° GRAPE pulse. a) A calibration matrix (L) is computed to adjust the standardized universal pulse (SUP) designed over the standardized pulse design database to the subject $B1^+$ map. Its magnitude is close to the identity matrix while diagonal phase terms are close to 0 radian. b) RF and gradient amplitudes of the resulting adjusted SUP. c and d) Flip angle maps and histograms retrospectively simulated on the subject for the UP and adjusted SUP with the subject's full $B1^+$ map. NRMSEs are 9.5% and 7.5%, respectively.

Figure 2: Boxplots of the subject-wise flip angle normalized root mean square error (FA-NRMSE) and normalized mean FA ($\langle FA \rangle$) simulated with Bloch equations over a test database of 15 subjects. Adjusted SUPs show improved performance compared to UPs in terms of FA-NRMSE ($NRMSE_{adjSUP}=6.4\%$ vs $NRMSE_{UP}=8.0\%$ for the 8° pulse and $NRMSE_{adjSUP}=0.67\%$ vs $NRMSE_{UP}=0.85\%$ for the 180° pulse) and normalized mean ($\langle FA_{adjSUP} \rangle / 8 = 0.99$ vs $\langle FA_{UP} \rangle / 8 = 1.01$ for the 8° pulse and $\langle FA_{adjSUP} \rangle / 180 = 0.997$ vs $\langle FA_{UP} \rangle / 180 = 0.995$ for the 180° pulse), along with less outliers and reduced inter-subject variability.

Figure 3: Sagittal view of the MPRAGE sequence run on a volunteer with a) universal pulses (UP) and b) adjusted standardized UPs (SUP). Adjusted SUP image shows a more homogeneous signal compared to UP, especially in the frontal lobe.

Figure 4: a) UNI contrast computed from the two inversion volumes of the MP2RAGE sequence acquired with the adjusted SUP. b to d) T1 map computed by injecting UNI signal intensities and sequence parameters in Bloch equation simulations for the MP2RAGE sequence acquired in the CP mode, CP mode with B1⁺ correction and adjusted SUP, respectively. e) T1 histograms values extracted from the brain for figures 4c and 4d, showing an impact on the distributions.